

Ambisearchers: Search Modalities and Algorithmic Awareness

Meghan L. Dowell^a

^a *University of Kentucky, Lexington, Kentucky, USA*

1. Introduction

This study investigates the relationship between how users access search engines, referred to as search modality, and their understanding of how algorithms curate search results. The research highlights the emergence of a new digital divide, termed the "algorithmic divide," which distinguishes between individuals who are aware of algorithmic curation and those who are not (Cotter & Reisdorf, 2020; Gran et al., 2020). We introduce the concept of "ambisearchers" to describe users who utilize multiple devices to access search engines, arguing for a broader perspective on digital divides that extends beyond mere access to technology.

A significant portion of Americans now access the internet via smartphones, not only for social media but also for information retrieval (Pew Research Center, 2024). Paralleling social media algorithms that tailor content based on user data, search engine algorithms also use personal information to curate search results, a process that is often opaque to the user, except through privacy policies and observed phenomena. This lack of awareness contributes to the algorithmic divide, a phenomenon that exists even as traditional digital divides related to internet and computer access have evolved (van Dijk, 2020). Search modality influences how users interact with search engines and the resulting search results, meaning the same query might yield different results on a mobile phone versus a laptop. Neither the ACRL's Framework for Information Literacy nor IFLA's Guidelines on Information Literacy for Lifelong Learning have yet to fully addressed the impact of search modality (Koenig, 2020; Powers, 2017).

The research aims to contribute evidence for changes in information literacy education and to underscore the importance of data protection policies that inform users about algorithmic curation. It specifically investigates how different search modalities impact the type of information users encounter. The study poses two key research questions: (1) Does user demographics relate to search modality? and (2) Does awareness of algorithmic curation differ based on search modality?.

2. Methodology

The study employed a survey instrument developed by analyzing Google's privacy policy to understand how personal information is used for algorithmic curation. The survey included questions about actions influencing search results and the types of personal data collected. This approach aimed for specific recollection rather than generalized assessments of algorithmic awareness. Data was collected in January 2022 through Qualtrics' research panel, with demographic quotas aligning with the 2020 US Census. The survey covered internet usage and algorithmic awareness across Google Search, Facebook, and YouTube, with this article focusing on search engine users.

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EMAIL: meghan.dowell@uky.edu (A. 1)

ORCID: 0000-0002-8740-5873 (A. 1)

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3. Results

The results identified four types of searchers based on their access methods: ambisearchers (multiple devices), mobile searchers (mobile only), computer searchers (desktops, laptops, tablets), and voice searchers (virtual assistants). Ambisearchers constituted 40% of the sample, followed by mobile searchers (35%), computer searchers (20%), and voice searchers (5%). Mobile searchers primarily use mobile data for internet access, while ambisearchers use broadband or unlimited mobile data. Voice searchers showed an unexpectedly high reliance on satellite internet access, warranting further investigation. The purposes of searches were fairly evenly distributed, with ambisearchers being more prominent in searches related to work tasks.

Demographic analysis revealed that gender identity was relatively even across modalities, except for voice search, where 71% of respondents were women. Ambisearchers and mobile searchers were more likely to be aged 25-44, while computer searchers were predominantly 60 and older. Voice search users were more evenly distributed among those aged 25 and older, with a slight overrepresentation in the 45-59 age group. Education levels varied significantly, with 75% of mobile-only searchers and 94% of voice-only searchers being non-college graduates, compared to a more even split for ambisearchers.

Regarding algorithmic curation awareness, a majority (60%) of participants were aware that Google uses personal information to customize search results. However, awareness varied by search modality, with ambisearchers showing higher than expected awareness and computer and voice searchers showing lower than expected awareness. Notably, 44% of voice searchers answered "no" to this question. When asked if two people would get the same search results for the same query at the same time, overall awareness decreased. While ambisearchers still showed the highest percentage of awareness, it dropped significantly, suggesting a lack of understanding of how personal data specifically affects search results. Ambisearchers also reported a much higher awareness of Google having a privacy policy compared to other modalities, while mobile and voice searchers had higher rates of uncertainty or belief that no such policy existed.

4. Discussion

The study underscores the importance of considering the shift of younger users towards social media platforms for information retrieval, which present a more limited and potentially more biased set of information compared to traditional search engines. This necessitates a targeted approach to information literacy education that acknowledges different types of searchers. The increasing prevalence of generative AI in information seeking further emphasizes the need for evolving digital and information literacy curricula to include multimodal searching. Users often learn about algorithmic systems through experience, peer discussions, or formal education, as platforms provide limited transparency (DeVito et al., 2017). Socioeconomic factors contribute to gaps in algorithmic knowledge, highlighting the need for public education.

While search modality may not be the sole driver of awareness, there are significant differences in algorithmic awareness based on how users access search engines. Ambisearchers demonstrate higher algorithmic awareness than single-modality searchers. Research indicate that searchers often perceive search algorithms as neutral and objective, which is impossible (Haider & Rödl, 2023; Haider & Sundin, 2019). This difference has important implications for information literacy standards and policies aimed at mitigating digital divides. Demographic variables like age and education level are associated with search modality. Educational interventions for digital literacies are less common for older adults. Data suggests that the access point for information retrieval significantly impacts digital literacies. The combination of search modality and algorithmic knowledge contributes to a digital divide. If single-modality searchers, particularly mobile and voice users, assume that the first results are the most relevant, further efforts are needed to enhance their algorithmic knowledge. Additional research is needed on voice-only searchers to better understand their characteristics and algorithmic awareness. Future research should also explore search revision behaviors and satisfaction among voice searchers to provide a more comprehensive understanding of how modality impacts information divides. As

smartphone and smart speaker ownership grows and reliance on cellular data increases, digital literacies must evolve to address the lack of awareness regarding algorithmic curation.

5. References

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